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Assessment of N-Power Teachers' Job Performance in Kwara State

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ABSTRACT

The N-Power programme is a Nigerian government initiative aimed at reducing unemployment and improving educational quality through the deployment of young graduates as teachers in public primary schools. Despite its potential, concerns remain about the effectiveness of N-Power teachers in enhancing learning outcomes. Consequently, this study assessed the performance of N-Power teachers in basic schools in Kwara State, Nigeria, using four research questions. A descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. The population comprised all permanent teachers in Kwara State, while the target population included teachers in basic schools across five Local Government Areas—Asa, Moro, Ilorin South, Ilorin West, and Ilorin East. Using a proportionate sampling technique (40%), 42 basic schools were selected, after which simple random sampling was employed to select 10 teachers from each school, yielding a total of 420 respondents. Data were collected using a researcher-designed instrument titled *N-Power Teacher Performance Questionnaire (NTPQ)*. Face validity was established, and reliability testing using Cronbach Alpha produced a coefficient of 0.81, confirming the instrument's reliability. The findings revealed that most N-Power teachers possessed either a bachelor's degree or NCE, with science and education degrees being predominant. The study also showed frequent use of positive classroom management strategies but revealed low to moderate levels of teacher commitment. The study recommended collaborative efforts by federal and state governments to provide targeted training and incentives for professional teaching qualifications.

Keyword: N-Power, Teachers' Job Performance, Basic schools

INTRODUCTION

Nigeria is endowed with abundant human and natural resources, positioning it as one of Africa's leading economies based on Gross Domestic Product (GDP). However, economic performance and societal well-being are influenced by various factors such as population size, income distribution, inflation, debt levels, and human development indicators. Despite a decline in unemployment from 5.3% in 2022 to 4.1% in the first quarter of 2023, followed by a slight increase to 4.2% by the end of the second quarter (National Bureau of Statistics [NBS], 2023), poverty remains prevalent, affecting 73% of the population, with 74 out of every 100 Nigerians living below the poverty line of 137,430 Naira annually (National Bureau of Statistics, 2023).

The World Bank reports that as of 2023, poverty and unemployment rates in Nigeria remain persistently high, forecasting a modest economic growth of 2.9% with a projected reduction in poverty to 71.9% (World Bank, 2023). Nevertheless, the World Bank has emphasized the necessity for Nigeria to enact comprehensive reforms and policies aimed at stimulating economic recovery, reducing poverty and unemployment rates, and enhancing social services (World Bank, 2023). Of particular concern is the disproportionate level of youth unemployment, as highlighted by the National Bureau of Statistics (NBS, 2023). Abu (2015) underscores that Nigeria's primary challenge lies in addressing youth unemployment, a sentiment echoed by Olubusoye et al. (2022), who argue that youth unemployment is predominantly structural rather than cyclical or frictional, thereby explaining its persistent increase despite mitigation efforts.

Unemployment reduction stands as a pivotal campaign promise of President Muhammadu Buhari's current administration. In response to the persistent issue of youth redundancy, the government introduced N-Power as part of the National Social Investment Programme of Nigeria. This initiative aims to create jobs and empower young Nigerians aged between 18 and 35 years. Recognizing that skills and knowledge drive economic growth and social development, the government launched N-Power in 2016, deploying 200,000 young Nigerians to public primary schools, primary healthcare centers, and agricultural development projects across all Local Government Areas nationwide. An additional 300,000 young graduates were enlisted in 2017, bringing the total number of beneficiaries to 500,000. Despite these substantial figures, questions arise regarding whether N-Power, amidst various strategies by past administrations, can effectively achieve its goal of youth empowerment, or if unemployment will persist and even escalate unchecked.

Education has been globally acknowledged as a catalyst for national development and transformation (Federal Republic of Nigeria, 2004). In line with this recognition, the federal government of Nigeria has taken upon itself the duty to oversee the management of this transformative tool of change and national development, as emphasized in President Nixon's 1970 speech, which famously stated:

Basic education, provided to children aged 6 to 15 through primary and junior secondary schools, serves as the cornerstone upon which the entire educational system hinges. This pivotal role underscores the necessity for stakeholders to prioritize laying a robust foundation for its sustainability (Etor et al., 2013). In Nigeria, this concept has evolved from six years of primary schooling to encompass an additional three years of junior secondary education. Umoh (2006) asserts that for basic education to effectively underpin the educational system, it must impart elementary and comprehensive scientific knowledge, equipping learners with practical skills in using scientific tools and devices. Just as a shaky foundation compromises the integrity of a building, the quality of teachers in basic education plays a crucial role in establishing a durable framework for the entire educational sector.

The teacher plays a pivotal role as the facilitator of learning, essential for achieving the educational goals and aims. They hold the key to students' academic success; their effective use of this key establishes a solid foundation, particularly at the primary level, underscoring the necessity for thorough teacher training (FRN, 2004). The Federal Republic of Nigeria recognizes that the quality of teacher education directly impacts the overall quality of the education system. Teachers are central not only to shaping future careers but also to sustaining the global economy's ecosystem for growth and stability. The ultimate aim is to ensure living conditions and resource utilization meet human needs without compromising system integrity and stability. Thus, it is crucial to reassess the N-POWER Teach scheme within the framework of a renewed vision of Education For All (EFA) and equitable social development (Okoro & Bassey, 2018). Teaching is not only fundamental to individual life but also vital for national progress and development. However, if professionals from other fields are to participate in the N-POWER Teach program, the goal should be to familiarize them with the teaching profession and deepen their understanding of societal challenges across generations (Okoro & Bassey, 2018).

The initiative by the federal government of Nigeria through the N-Power scheme to enhance basic education delivery is commendable, yet it requires careful review, particularly in terms of adequate training. The N-Power Teachers scheme was devised to deploy empowered youth as teacher assistants in schools across Nigeria, with the intention of supporting existing teachers rather than replacing them. These assistants are tasked with aiding in teaching activities, school management, and other

school-related functions (N-Power Informational Guide, 2017). Additionally, they are encouraged to extend basic education to children in remote and marginalized communities where educational access is limited (Aderonmu, 2017).

However, the implementation of the N-Power Teacher scheme must consider the social, environmental, and economic dimensions of human development and their relationship with education. Effective education empowerment involves building sustainable human and material resources. Ensuring that N-Power teachers are adequately prepared to teach goes beyond theoretical training; it requires practical, on-the-job preparation. Despite the scheme's intention for volunteers to act as assistants, the severe shortage of teachers has led many N-Power participants to assume full teaching responsibilities and even take on roles as subject heads.

N-Power

N-power is a job creation and empowerment programme of the National Social Investment Programme (NSIP) of the Federal Government of Nigeria (FGN). Basically, it is an employability and enhancement programme aimed at imbibing the learn-work-entrepreneurship culture in youth between the ages of 18 and 35. Indeed, the FGN aggressive investment in youth development targets some of the perennial inadequacies in public services such as low teacher to pupil ratio in public primary schools, high rate of preventable disease and lack of taxable persons within the tax net. And using N-POWER, the Nigeria government aims at utilizing a large volunteer work-force to fix some of the problems in public services as well as stimulating the larger economy (N-power informational guide, 2017).

Job Performance

Job performance can be described as the achievement of a particular task or the result of a particular task in line with laid down principles or guidelines. Yahaya (2009) defines job performance as an accomplishment of assigned duties in accordance with organization guidelines subject to the normal constants of reasonable utilization of available resources. Fabiyi (2000) also described teacher's job performance as a measurement of his/her teaching performance. Adana (2016), maintain that effective job performance provides the employee with economic gains, security, social status, family and social prerogative, medical benefits and recreational and educational opportunities. Abdullahi (2004) described teachers' job performance as the attitudes exhibited by teachers during the course of performing their official duties

Statement of the Problem

The N-Power program, a Nigerian government initiative addressing unemployment and educational enhancement through the deployment of young graduates as teachers in public primary schools, has placed a significant number of teachers in basic schools in Kwara State. While the program holds promise, concerns persist regarding the effectiveness of these N-Power teachers in improving learning outcomes. An assessment of their performance is imperative to ascertain whether they possess the requisite qualification, classroom management skill, and pedagogy for quality instruction delivery. Understanding their strengths and weaknesses is essential for targeted professional development programs to enhance their capabilities.

Furthermore, studies suggest that some N-Power teachers lack teaching experience and background to effectively handle learners, raising questions about the adequacy of the recruitment process (Owusu et al., 2021). The selection of N-Power teachers was not contingent upon possessing educational certificates recognized by the Teachers Registration Council of Nigeria (TRCN), casting doubt on the recruitment methods. Reports of teacher attrition in basic schools nationwide underscore the need to investigate the job performance of N-Power teachers (Subair & Talabi, 2015). This study seeks to address these gaps by examining the job performance of N-Power teachers as perceived by permanent teachers in Kwara State's basic schools, aiming to provide insights into their effectiveness and contribute to informed policy decisions regarding teacher recruitment and training.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of this study is to assess N-Power teachers' performance in Basic schools school teachers in Kwara state, Nigeria. Specifically, the study aims to:

- i. Examine the educational qualification profile of N-Power Teachers in Basic Schools in Kwara State.

- ii. Investigate the classroom management strategies employed by N-Power Teachers in Basic Schools as perceived by school teachers in Kwara State.
- iii. Assess the level of lesson preparation of N-Power Teachers in Basic Schools as perceived by school teachers in Kwara State.
- iv. Find out the extent of N-Power Teachers' commitment to teaching in Basic Schools as perceived by school teachers in Kwara State.

Research Questions

The following questions were raised to guide the study.

- i. What are the education qualifications profile of N-Power Teachers' in basic schools in Kwara State?
- ii. What are the classroom management strategies employed by N-Power Teachers in Basic Schools in Kwara State?
- iii. What is the level of lesson preparation of N-Power Teachers in Basic Schools in Kwara State?
- iv. What is the extent of N-Power Teachers commitment to teaching in Basic Schools in Kwara State?

METHODOLOGY

The research design adopted for this study was descriptive design of survey type. The population for this study comprised all permanent teachers in Kwara State. There are 9,677 teachers in Kwara State (National Bureau of Statistics, 2023). The target population comprised all permanent teachers in basic schools in five local government area (LGA) in Kwara State including; Asa, Moro, Ilorin South, Ilorin West and Ilorin East. Proportionate (40%) sampling technique was used to select 42 basic schools, which is approximated to be; Asa (5), Moro (5), Ilorin South (10), Ilorin west (12) and Ilorin East (10). Simple random sampling technique was then used to select 10 teachers from each selected basic schools in the targeted LGA bringing the total number of respondents to 420, which is within the range suggested by research advisor. The instruments that was used for this study is a researcher-designed questionnaire titled "Perceived N-power Teachers' Performance" questionnaire (PNTP). Validated by my supervisor and two lecturers from the department of Educational Management and three lecturers in the field of measurement and evaluation for face and content validity. The questionnaire was pilot-tested on 50 similar teachers, and a Cronbach Alpha reliability coefficient of 0.81 confirmed its suitability for the study. Frequency count was used to answer research question 1, research question 2 was answered using item-by-item mean analysis ranking order and research questions 3 and 4 were used using percentage analysis.

DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

Research Question One: *What is the education qualifications profile of N-Power Teachers' in basic schools in Kwara State?*

Table 1: Percentage analysis of the Educational qualification profile of N-Power Teachers in Kwara State

Qualification	Frequency	Percentage
NCE	113	26.9
OND	40	9.7
HND	85	20.2
B.Sc/Ed	151	35.9
Others	31	7.3
Total	420	100.0

Table 1 revealed the educational qualifications held by N-Power teachers within basic schools across Kwara State. Among the various qualifications, Bachelor's Degrees (B.Sc Ed) emerge as the predominant credential, constituting 35.9% of the total with 151 teachers. Following closely behind is the Nigerian Certificate in Education (NCE), held by 113 teachers, making up 26.9% of the total. Additionally, 85 teachers possess a Higher National Diploma (HND), representing 20.2% of the total,

while 40 teachers, comprising 9.7%, hold the least prevalent qualification, the Ordinary National Diploma (OND). Moreover, 31 teachers, accounting for 7.3%, possess qualifications not falling into the aforementioned categories. Overall, the data underscores a trend wherein a substantial proportion of N-Power teachers in Kwara State's basic schools hold either a bachelor's degree or a diploma, with the Bachelor's degree in Education emerging as the most prevalent qualification.

Research Question Two: *What are the classroom management strategies employed by N Power Teachers in Basic Schools in Kwara State?*

Table 2: Classroom Management Strategies Employed By N-Power Teachers in Basic Schools in Kwara State

Classroom Management Strategies	Mean	Rank	Remark
Rule Communication Mastery	3.23	1 st	Employed
Positive Reinforcement Prowess	3.10	2 nd	Employed
Proactive Disruption Prevention	3.06	3 rd	Employed
Transition Management Excellence	2.98	4 th	Employed
Instructional Engagement Versatility	2.95	5 th	Employed
Conflict Resolution Expertise	2.86	6 th	Employed
Community Building Proficiency	2.81	7 th	Employed
Non-verbal Cue Utilization	2.62	8 th	Employed
Consistent Consequence Application	2.59	9 th	Employed
Feedback-driven Adaptation	2.51	10 th	Employed

Table 2, N-Power teachers frequently employ a range of classroom management strategies, with the most utilized ones being Rule Communication Mastery, Positive Reinforcement Prowess, and Proactive Disruption Prevention, with mean scores of 3.23, 3.10, and 3.06, respectively. This indicates a strong emphasis on establishing clear rules, providing positive reinforcement, and pre-emptively addressing disruptions. These findings underscore the importance N-Power teachers place on cultivating a conducive and structured learning environment. Additionally, the Table reveals that N-Power teachers also implement other essential strategies such as Transition Management Excellence, Instructional Engagement Versatility, Conflict Resolution Expertise, and Community Building Proficiency with mean score of , 2.98, 2.95, 2.86, 2.81, 2.62, 2.59 and 2.51 respectively, albeit to a slightly lesser extent. These diverse strategies collectively contribute to fostering an environment conducive to effective teaching and learning.

Research Question Three: *What is the level of lesson preparation of N-Power Teachers in Basic Schools in Kwara State?*

Table 3: Lesson preparation of N-Power Teachers in Basic Schools in Kwara State

Levels	Score Range	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Low	21-32	151	35.9
Average	33-42	203	48.3
High	43-52	66	15.8
Total		420	100.0

Table 3 shows the lesson preparation level of N-Power teachers in Kwara State's basic schools, offering insights garnered from a survey encompassing 420 teachers. Among the surveyed cohort, a notable portion, amounting to 35.9% of the surveyed teachers, disclosed operating at a "low" level of preparation, scored within the range of 21 to 32. Nearly half, constituting 48.3%, reported maintaining an "average" level of preparation falling within the score range of 33 to 42. A smaller faction comprising 15.8% of the teachers reported a "high" level of preparation, reflected in a score range of 43 to 52. This means that the lesson preparation level of N-Power teachers in Kwara State's basic schools is average which implies that while these teachers may adhere to lesson plans, their preparation may lack the depth and innovation necessary for optimal classroom engagement.

Research Question Four: *What is the extent of N-Power Teachers commitment to teaching in Basic Schools in Kwara State?*

Table 4: Extent of N-Power Teachers commitment to teaching in Basic Schools in Kwara State

Extent	Score Range	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Low	33-42	193	45.9
Moderate	43-51	182	43.3
High	52-60	45	10.8
Total		420	100.0

Table 4 presents data on the commitment levels of N-Power teachers in Kwara State's basic schools. The commitment levels are categorized as low, moderate, and high, each assigned a specific score range. The table indicates that 193 out of 420 surveyed teachers (45.9%) fall into the low commitment category, with a score range of 33-42. Among the surveyed teachers, 182 (43.3%) demonstrate a moderate commitment level, falling within the score range of 43-51 and only 45 teachers (10.8%) exhibit a high level of commitment, scoring within the range of 52-60. From the data, it's evident that a significant portion of N-Power teachers in Kwara State's basic schools display either low or moderate levels of commitment to teaching.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

This study assessed N-power Teachers job performance in Basic schools in Kwara State. Findings from this study showed that a substantial proportion of N-Power teachers in Kwara State's basic schools hold either a bachelor's degree (35.9%) or a NCE (26.9%), with the Bachelor's degree in Science or Education emerging as the most prevalent qualification. This finding underscores the diverse educational backgrounds within the teaching cohort. This suggests a relatively well-educated teaching workforce, potentially equipped with subject-specific knowledge and pedagogical skills. This finding aligns with studies such as Ogunbayo and Mhlanga (2022), Kinsley and Omoregie (2020) which suggests that teacher qualifications, particularly advanced degrees, positively correlate with student achievement. However, it contrasts with the work of Coenen et al (2018), which challenges the notion that teacher credentials alone significantly impact student outcomes, emphasizing the importance of effective teaching practices over formal qualifications.

In addition, findings from this study revealed that N-Power teachers frequently employ a range of classroom management strategies, with the most utilized ones being Rule Communication Mastery, Positive Reinforcement Prowess, and Proactive Disruption Prevention. This finding highlights N-Power teachers' proactive approach to maintaining order and fostering a conducive learning environment. This suggests a recognition of the importance of effective classroom management in facilitating student engagement and learning. This finding is supported by a study of Alasmari and Althaqafi (2021), which emphasizes the positive impact of proactive and positive classroom management strategies on student behavior and academic achievement. However, it contrasts with the findings of a study by Owusu et al (2021) and Korpershoek et al. (2016), which suggests that the effectiveness of classroom management strategies may vary depending on factors such as teacher-student relationships and cultural contexts, indicating a need for further exploration of the nuanced dynamics at play in classroom management practices.

Furthermore, the study demonstrated that the lesson preparation level of N-Power teachers in Kwara State's basic schools is average (48.3%), which implies that while these teachers may adhere to lesson plans, their preparation may lack the depth and innovation necessary for optimal classroom engagement. This indicates a need for further support and professional development to enhance the quality of lesson planning and delivery. This finding resonates with a study by Ayres, (2014), which underscores the significance of thorough lesson planning in promoting effective teaching practices and student learning outcomes. However, it contrasts with the findings of a study by Santoyo and Zhang (2016) , which suggests that the impact of lesson planning on student achievement may not be as substantial as other factors such as teacher-student relationships and feedback, urging a more comprehensive examination of the multifaceted nature of teaching effectiveness.

Moreover, the study indicated that a significant portion of N-Power teachers in Kwara State's basic schools display either low (45.9%) or moderate (43.3%) levels of commitment to teaching. This finding' raises concerns about the quality and sustainability of education delivery among N-Power teachers within the region. This suggests potential issues with teacher motivation, engagement, or support systems that may hinder their effectiveness in the classroom. The prevalence of low to moderate commitment levels underscores the importance of addressing underlying factors such as workload, professional development opportunities, and job satisfaction to improve teacher performance. This finding aligns with research by Nieves and Williams (2011), which highlights the negative impact of teacher turnover and dissatisfaction on student achievement and school effectiveness. However, it contrasts with a study by Wang and Gao (2020) which suggests that teacher commitment alone may not necessarily correlate with student outcomes, emphasizing the need to consider broader contextual factors and instructional practices in assessing educational quality.

CONCLUSIONS

This study on the assessment of N-Power teachers' performance in Kwara State's basic schools reveals a nuanced landscape characterized by varying levels of commitment, lesson preparation, and classroom management strategies among N-power teachers. While a significant proportion of teachers demonstrate average levels of lesson preparation and employ diverse classroom management techniques, concerns arise regarding the substantial presence of low to moderate commitment levels among N-Power teachers. These findings underscore the importance of targeted interventions and support mechanisms to enhance teacher effectiveness and promote positive student outcomes in Kwara State's basic schools. Addressing factors contributing to low commitment levels and providing opportunities for professional development and mentorship can play a crucial role in improving the overall quality of education delivery within Kwara State.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings that emanated from this study, the following recommendations were made:

1. The Federal Government, overseeing the N-Power program, could consider offering targeted training programs or incentives to encourage N-Power teachers with non-education degrees to pursue teaching qualifications like the Post Graduate Diploma in Education (PGDE) or Nigerian Certificate in Education (NCE).
2. The State Government's education department could organize workshops or professional development programs specifically focused on classroom management.
3. School authorities can implement peer-mentoring programs where high-scoring teachers with well-developed lesson plans can share their strategies and resources with colleagues in the "average" preparation category.
4. The Federal Government, in conjunction with the State Government and school authorities, could conduct surveys or focus groups to understand the reasons behind low or moderate teacher commitment.

REFERENCES

- Aderonmu, J.A., (2017). *Poverty eradication in rural Nigeria: The role of local Government*. A paper presented at a Conference on "Empowerment of Rural People" organized by Charity Centre for Advancement and Rural Empowerment, Abuja in Jos, 6-8 December.
- Alasmari, N. J., & Althaqafi, A. S. A. (2021). Teachers' practices of proactive and reactive classroom management strategies and the relationship to their self-efficacy. *Language Teaching Research*, 13621688211046352.
- Ayres, J. (2014). Lesson planning: Outcomes and responsibilities in planning. *Center for Teaching Excellence*.
- Coenen, J., Cornelisz, I., Groot, W., Maassen van den Brink, H., & Van Klaveren, C. (2018). Teacher characteristics and their effects on student test scores: A systematic review. *Journal of Economic Surveys*, 32(3), 848–877.
- Etor R. C, Usen F.M & Ekpenyong E. E (2013). Primary Education as a Foundation for Qualitative Higher Education in Nigeria. *Journal of Education and Learning*; 2(2).

- Fabiya, O. B. (2000). *Increasing productivity in Nigeria. Proceeding of the first National Conference on productivity*. Macmillan Publishers.
- Federal Republic of Nigeria. (2004). National Policy on Education. NERDC.
- Kingsley, I., and Omoregie, N. (2020). The Influence of Teachers Qualifications on Academic Performance of Secondary School Students in Delta State. *African Scholars Journal of Contemporary Education Research (JCER-8)*, 19(8), 207-220.
- Korpershoek, H., Harms, T., de Boer, H., van Kuijk, M., & Doolaard, S. (2016). A meta-analysis of the effects of classroom management strategies and classroom management programs on students' academic, behavioral, emotional, and motivational outcomes. *Review of Educational Research*, 86(3), 643–680.
- National Bureau of Statistics, Volume 1: *Unemployment and Underemployment report (Q4 2015 -Q3 2018)*
- Nieves, J., & Williams, T. (2011). Investigating the impact of organizational commitment on teacher job performance: A path analytic approach. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 27(4), 765-773.
- N-Power Informational Guide (2017). *Federal Government of Nigeria Social Investment Programme*
- Ogunbayo, S. B., & Mhlanga, N. (2022). Effects of Training on Teachers' Job Performance in Nigeria's Public Secondary Schools. *Asian Journal of Assessment in Teaching and Learning*, 12(1), 44-51. <https://doi.org/10.37134/ajatel.vol12.1.5.2022>.
- Okoro S.N and Basse U.E(2018). N-Power Teachers Competence and Resource Utilization: Implication for Effective and Efficient Teaching in Nigerian Primary and Post Primary School. *International Journal of Education and Evaluation*, 4 (1). www.iiardpub.org
- Olubusoye O.E, Salisu A.A & Olofin O.O(2022). Youth Unemployment in Nigeria: nature, causes, and solutions. *Quality & Quantity* 57,1125-1157. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11135-022-01388-8>
- Owusu, M. K., Dramanu, B. Y., & Amponsah, M. O. (2021). Classroom management strategies and academic performance of junior high school students. *Int. J. Educ. Manag. Eng*, 11, 29–38.
- Santoyo, C., & Zhang, S. (2016). Secondary teacher candidates' lesson planning learning. *Teacher Education Quarterly*, 43(2), 3–27.
- Subair S.T & Talabi R.B (2015). Teacher Shortage in Nigerin Schools: Causes, effects and administrators coping strategies. *Asia Pacific Journal of Education, Arts and Sciences* 2(4), 31-37, 2015.
- Wang, Y., & Gao, P. (2020). The relationship between organizational commitment and job performance: A meta-analysis. *Human Resource Development Review*, 19(4), 390-426.